

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan (D5.1)

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Document history

Changes		
v1.0	12/03/2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Initial version
V1.1	24/03/2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Updated list of events and communication channels

Introduction

This dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan presents the strategy and methodology for dissemination and exploitation activities in the HORIZON-ZEN Plus project. The plan focuses on creating awareness of the project results through targeted dissemination activities to EU programme beneficiaries.

Objective

The primary objective of the dissemination, exploitation and communication plan is to **stimulate the uptake of project results by EU programme beneficiaries** and to foster the integration of best practices among key target groups for exploitation.

Resources

The project operates with constrained resources, approximately 1 person-month (PM), dedicated to communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. Therefore, it primarily depends on the integration of activities presented in this plan into pre-existing initiatives.

Key assets

Below is a summary of the essential dissemination and communication assets that HORIZON-ZEN Plus utilizes for its dissemination activities.

Brand and visual identity

The EOR-community is a Zenodo-community setup and **managed by the European Commission**, and is as such clearly branded with the EU's visual identity.

The EOR-community is not branded with any EOSC branding.

Dissemination partners

Dissemination partners	
OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE has built up a strong dissemination team and channels in particular in terms of support to EU programme beneficiaries, and is thus a key dissemination partner.
European Commission	The EC has the most direct channels to the EU programme beneficiaries and can integrate results from the project into the communication to beneficiaries. In addition, the EC project officers have direct contact with the project coordinators and can provide presentations to the projects and thus work as

	important multipliers. Last, the EC's graphics design team can help with visuals.
CERN	CERN itself has multiple communications teams, however their primary target audience is the general public and hence not aligned with the primary target audience for the project.
EU beneficiaries	The adopters are EU beneficiaries which each have their own dissemination plans, as well as potential institutional communications teams that can help dissemination results.
InvenioRDM partners	The 30+ InvenioRDM partners are both a target audience, but can also act as dissemination partners in particular with respect to disseminating best practices and support the exploitation of the project results.

Communication channels

Following are the key communication channels by which we intend to disseminate the project results:

- Social media (primarily X, previously Twitter):
 - [@OpenAIRE_EU](#) (17.2k followers)
 - [@CERN](#) (2.4M followers)
- [Zenodo Blog](#) including [HORIZON-ZEN Plus project page](#).
- [Zenodo Newsletter](#)
- [OpenAIRE Newsletter](#)
- [OpenAIRE Webinars](#)
- [OpenAIRE Factsheets](#)
- EC email notification to programme beneficiaries
- EC webinar for EC project officers
- EC press releases
- CERN press releases

Conferences/Events

The following are key conferences/events where we will try to position the project results in collaboration with existing initiatives:

- EOSC Symposium (November 2025)
- [InvenioRDM Workshop \(February 2026\)](#)
- EOSC Symposium (October 2026)
- [Open Repositories \(June 2026\)](#)
- [OHBM 2026](#)
- Open Science FAIR 2027

- EU Research & Innovation Days 2026 + 2027

Strategy and methodology

The project has only limited efforts available within the project itself for communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, and thus relies heavily on integration of the described activities into existing initiatives. By harnessing the expertise of communication entities such as OpenAIRE or optimizing impact through strategic selection of a few prominent channels (e.g., leveraging the social reach of EC/CERN), we are confident that we can attain a substantial outreach for the EOR-Community.

Target audiences

1. EU research programme beneficiaries (primary audience)

The key target audience is **EU programme beneficiaries**. We categorize programme beneficiaries very broadly in two classes:

- Existing users of EOR in Zenodo: programme beneficiaries that already have one or more EOR-communities for one or more EC funded projects.
- New users of Zenodo - programme beneficiaries without any existing EOR-community for their project.

Existing users

Existing users often have a project member designated by the project to manage the EOR-community. The person may be in charge of managing and uploading all content, or may rely on other project members to help submit content to the repository. Overall existing users may have widely varying degrees of adoption and acceptance of the usage of the community within a project.

Existing users/communities of Zenodo are a very heterogeneous community from all fields of science.

New users

New users are programme beneficiaries which either have decided for an alternative solution or lack knowledge/information about Zenodo and the EOR-community.

2. InvenioRDM partners

InvenioRDM partners have a direct vested interest in the outcomes of the project, as most of the results will be integrated into InvenioRDM. They serve as co-design partners and thus need to be kept informed and consulted about the project. Also, InvenioRDM partners can serve as multipliers of dissemination activities.

3. Open Science stakeholders

We group EOSC trusted repositories, EOSC service & tools providers, institutional repositories, open-source repository platforms and funders into open science stakeholders. While each group has different interests and can be reached by different dissemination channels, the messaging will be similar in that they want to be informed about the impact of the project.

Campaigns

Overall, the project's dissemination and communication activities will be primarily directed towards the primary target audience to focus efforts on the adoption of the project results. This will allow us to collect success stories to demonstrate the impact and usefulness of the results to secondary target audiences.

The secondary audiences will be integrated on a best-effort basis into dissemination activities, and will primarily be addressed in the latter part of the project. The documented success stories are a key asset for dissemination to these target audiences.

Dissemination

Phases

We've divided the dissemination activities into 5 phases aligned with the release milestones of the project:

- Release 1 – Support automation
- Release 2 – AI-assisted curation
- Release 3 – ORE and EOSC EU Node integration
- Release 4 – FAIR and AI-ready datasets
- Release 5 – Enhanced search and discovery workflows

Each phase will include at least release notes, a blog post or a newsletter.

Additionally, two user surveys will be conducted throughout the project, in Q2 2026 and Q3 2027.

Activities

Dissemination will happen through the channels described on key assets and through the following activities

OpenAIRE newsletter/webinars

The OpenAIRE webinar and newsletter are key dissemination channels for reaching our target group.

OpenAIRE factsheets/guides

OpenAIRE has developed several factsheets (1, 2) about Zenodo, as well as [open science training and guides for Horizon Europe](#). We aim at continuing integrating the EOR-community into these guides on open science.

Frontpage

We will continue featuring and highlighting the EOR-community on the Zenodo-frontpage. Similarly the EOR-community frontpage will be a key channel for updates on new product features throughout the project.

Guides & Training material

Every guide and training material is published on help.zenodo.org.

Plan

Below is an overview of planned dissemination activities throughout the project.:

Activity	Description	Schedule
Project page	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project page public on zenodo.org with a description of the project 	October 2025
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Symposium 2025 	November 2025
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> InvenioRDM Partners Meeting 2026 	February 2026
Newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOR frontpage with each release (x5) 	April 2026 July 2026 October 2026 March 2027 July 2027
OpenAIRE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setup quarterly calls with OpenAIRE to plan dissemination activities. 	Quarterly
Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EOSC Symposium 2026 	October 2026
Webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Webinars: HORIZON-ZEN+ targets to include project results into webinars for programme beneficiaries organised by dissemination partners. 	TBD
Demo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrator to showcase how the enhancements made to the EOR Repository improve and simplify the support for FAIR and AI-ready datasets from a HE researcher's perspective 	September 2027

Communication

Sender

Under the HORIZON-ZEN Plus project, communication messages could be sent from two sources: Zenodo and the European Commission. When a message is sent, it is important to clearly indicate which of these two is the sender. In general, each communication channel is usually associated with a single sender.

Messaging

Target audience	Messages
EU beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trusted repository solution for EU projects at your fingertips. • Built in compliance with EU open science policy. • Easy open and FAIR publishing solution. • Enhanced discoverability of ML/AI-ready datasets. • AI-assisted submission and curation.
EOSC trusted repositories Institutional repositories Open-source repository platforms Funders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testbed for FAIR principles enablers in repositories. • FAIR assistance through UX design. • Compliance with Horizon Europe Grant Agreements. • Supporting the EU Open Science policy as part of EOSC.

Exploitation

The main technical and commercial impacts of HORIZON-ZEN Plus is achieved by integrating and deploying/releasing all project results into TRL9 services/products (Zenodo and the EOR Repository) thus ensuring all project results will be used after the project itself has finished.

The exploitation will primarily focus on updating the long-term sustainability plan for the EOR Repository and rely on the existing exploitation of Zenodo and InvenioRDM. The sustainability plan of previous Horizon Zen project is published here <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17143932>.

Monitoring and evaluation

An analysis of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be conducted to offer a holistic perspective on the extent of dissemination and communication executed throughout the project releases. This evaluation aims to measure the impact of these outreach efforts on the overall project outcomes.

As depicted in the table presented below, a suite of KPIs will delineate the extent of dissemination and communication, contrasting them with KPIs that quantify the tangible impact of these activities. Recognizing the inherent challenges in measuring impact for certain activities, we have incorporated generic impact KPIs that encapsulate the collective influence of all activities.

A snapshot of KPIs will be captured on a regular basis, specifically gathering KPIs for each release shortly before the subsequent software release.

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPIS	TARGET AT M24
Views of newsletter per release announcements (5 campaigns)	from 900 to 2000 per campaign
Documentation pages visits	3000 visitors per month
Webinars organised by dissemination partners	2 webinars
Conference presentations with HORIZON-ZEN+ results	2-4 conferences